

DETERMINATION METHODS OF FACTORS AFFECTING PIGGYBACK TRANSPORTATION

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ABSTRACT. The management of intermodal transportation is a complex and responsible process. Rail transport is traditionally used in the implementation of international and intercontinental piggyback transportation. The task of rail transport is to provide transportation over the so-called "land bridges" - land sections on which the route begins and ends, or through which it transits. Despite a significant level of computerization and informatization, the level of delays in the delivery of goods in the field of piggyback intermodal transportation is not decreasing. The unsatisfactory speed of piggyback trains is a significant factor in these delays. This problem is of common nature, and not faced by intermodal operators operating only in the Siberian and Eurasian continental land bridges, which pass through the territory of Russia and Kazakhstan, respectively, and deliver goods from Japan. It also applies to the American and Canadian land bridges, through which Japanese goods reach consumers in the United States and Canada, and through the ports of Germany and the Netherlands - to consumers in Western Europe. This situation has developed due to the lack of effective approaches to building management systems that would demonstrate a high level

of efficiency in the face of uncertainty, which is a natural component of the transportation process. The article is devoted to the correlation analysis of factors affecting the cargo turnover of piggyback transportation in the Republic of Uzbekistan. The main factors affecting the cargo turnover of piggyback transportation were identified; the degree of the effect was established by statistical methods. Based on data obtained for the last ten years, a correlation matrix and a regression model of cargo turnover were built. The results obtained make it possible to build forecasts for the cargo turnover of piggyback transportation from two to four years with a 95% confidence interval.

Keywords: multimodal transportation, factor analysis, regression model

1. INTRODUCTION

The most common types of cargo transport in the Republic of Uzbekistan are road and rail transportation. The road and railway networks are the foundations for the development, specialization, and concentration of industrial production, mining and agriculture. In addition, the developed transport infrastructure contributes to the fulfillment of one of the most important and very profitable tasks of the national economy, determined by the geographical position of the Republic of Uzbekistan, namely, to serve as a transport artery between Europe and the countries of Southeast Asia. To accomplish this task, not only new modern sections of roads and railways should be built on the territory of the republic but also transport hubs, container terminals, and appropriate infrastructure [1]. In addition, the national transport system, in particular, Joint Stock Company (JSC) "Uzbekiston temir yullari" (Uzbek railways) - the main railway company in the republic, should master modern logistics technologies, such as intermodal transportation, a significant part of which is piggyback transportation, the characteristic features of which are studied in this article.

Piggyback transportation is a service of transportation by one vehicle of another vehicle. The most widespread are in the railway industry, when trailers, euro trucks with trailers, contrailers, etc. are transported on specially equipped

wagons. After being removed from the platform, they can continue on their own on highways. The history of piggyback transportation on the railway network in the Republic of Uzbekistan is not so long and the first stage was limited to transit piggyback transportation. Over time, investments in this sector of the economy made it possible to equip several piggyback yards in container terminals, and at the end of 2021, such yards were built in 24% of terminals [2-3]. This has enabled national transport companies to participate in piggyback schemes, leading to appreciable savings in transport costs (as has long been proven by successful piggyback runs in other countries), and to a reduction in the carbon footprint of the industry, as the carbon footprint of products (CFP) transported by road is on average 83 times greater than CFP of rail transport [4]. The piggyback transportation technology is widely used in almost all European countries, including developed foreign countries. In recent years, the share of this type of transport on the railways of East Asia and Russia has been increasing. Currently, in a number of countries, due to restrictions on the movement of the trucks, there are cases of an increase in the time of delivery of goods to their destination. A temporary or complete ban on the movement of vehicles on Saturdays, Sundays, holidays, and restrictions on the weight of cargo on routes, negatively affect the quality of cargo transportation. Therefore, the need to use modern modes of transport in the system of cargo transportation is increasing every day.

In the scientific research by [5], the processing time for piggyback trains was determined and typical models of schemes for piggyback terminals were developed. A new classification of the railway was worked out based on existing freight stations with freight terminals. The time spent in the train was studied and a technological schedule was drawn up. The article shows the location of the truck on the railway platform and the wheel mounting points for the safe use of trailer terminals. The definition of the reliability criterion is considered. A mathematical model was developed for optimizing the placement of piggyback terminals at railway stations; a methodology was developed for determining the economic efficiency of processing piggyback trains at the station and piggyback terminals.

Kirillova in [6-7] on the basis of multimodal analysis, considered the issue of piggyback transport methods based on the improvement of road and rail communications. She offered mathematical optimization models for solving problems of piggyback routes, railway transport networks and optimal placement, and the arrival of traffic flows to piggyback terminals through the coordinates of the shortest distance in mixed transport. For the transportation of goods over short distances, the contrailer in her work is guided by the choice of the location of the terminal network. The disadvantage of the proposed work is the choice of a place according to a single criterion of traffic flows, while such factors as infrastructure, capital and operating costs, and the transport development in the area of the terminal do not allow this.

Kuzmin in [8] defined the problems and necessary conditions for the development of piggyback technology and considered the criteria for choosing a piggyback system. Based on the method of analysis of hierarchies, an algorithm for choosing a control system was proposed. With the simulation model developed for a regional rail transport system, it is possible to determine the traffic demand conditions at the regional level and the configuration of the rail terminal network.

Shobanov in [9] proposed theoretical and methodological approaches to the assessment based on the principles of transport logistics, taking into account the main factors of piggyback transportation efficiency. In rail transport, the contrailer calculates the upper and lower limits of the fares by separate methods for each participant. In the process of cargo transportation, a system and criteria for transportation efficiency indices were developed. The technical, technological, operational, and economic features of a comprehensive assessment of the effectiveness of piggyback transport were studied and an algorithm was developed.

In [10] Shapkin considered a feasibility study of options for a technological scheme to provide the terminal with technical means, as well as the rational transportation of trailers over long distances. The contrailer develops a mathematical and economic model for the rational choice of the parameters of the transport system and the criteria for their evaluation. The download method given

in the article and considered optimal has now lost its relevance, fast download methods used nowadays are safe and have the ability to download and upload in parallel.

The study in [11] explored the parameters that affect the formation of content when piggyback trains are supplied for operation. A variant of the tabular model was considered, which is convenient for solving problems when drawing up an agreement between a consignor and a carrier. The contractor develops an algorithm for optimizing the set of trains for different values, based on data on the regularity level of collection of trucks at the terminal and other transport indices and technical capabilities. The created algorithm takes into account economic, technical, and technological aspects. It applies performance prediction techniques to develop an algorithm for the set of trains.

The problem of modeling transportation processes is considered by Manueva [12], Sapozhnikov [13], Tsyganov [14], Popov [15] Rakhmangulov [16]. As for the issue of transport process modeling, programming by simulation is considered a good method.

In addition, Rezer [17], Sirazetdinov [18], and others developed research models for substantiating the economic efficiency of piggyback transportation.

There are gaps in the work on the most rational type of proposed piggyback terminal and the solution to the problem of placing terminals, taking into account infrastructure and costs. It is necessary to develop and systematically formulate a rational algorithm for piggyback transport technology.

Based on the analysis of the results of domestic and foreign practice, it can be noted that the scientific and practical research work conducted for many years to improve railway transport and develop combined modes of transportation in railway transport is insufficient. The development and practical application of innovative technologies for reloading goods from one mode of transport to another have not been sufficiently studied.

2. MATERIAL AND METHODS

In the analysis, a choice was made from the entire set of features associated with the transport available in the data set, some of their subset containing only the most significant features from the point of view of solving the problem, which will be used in the model as variables.

The significance here was in two aspects: relevance and redundancy. The first - features that were used to build a model that sufficiently influence piggyback transportation and reflect the dependencies and patterns of the study. The second - signs should not be correlated, i.e. carry the same information (for example, prices in dollars and in Uzbek sums). This problem is especially relevant for linear regression models, where insignificant and redundant variables not only increase the dimension of the problem without improving the quality of the solution, but also reduce the stability of the model.

Therefore, in order to build an adequate model, it is necessary to consider statistical data provided by the State Statistics Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan, which significantly affect piggyback transportation.

Annual cargo turnover of piggyback transportation in the Republic of Uzbekistan for the period 2012-2021 is shown in the graph, Figure. 1.

Source: compiled by the author based on data from (Annual reports, 2022)

Figure 1. Annual cargo turnover of piggyback transportation in the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2012-2021, million tons

Next, we consider the factors affecting the amount of piggyback cargo turnover in the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Since piggyback transportation is a promising direction for the development of cargo transport, with an increase in Gross Domestic Product (GDP) created in the transport industry, the cargo turnover of piggyback transportation should grow. The dynamics of the GDP of the transport industry in the Republic of Uzbekistan is shown in Figure. 2 [18].

Figure 2. GDP of the transport industry in the Republic of Uzbekistan for the period 2012-2021, billion USD

For the same reasons as above, the turnover of piggyback traffic, which by definition consists of road and rail transport, should depend on the amount of the corresponding cargo turnover, the dynamics of which is shown in Figure. 3 (State Committee, 2022)

Figure 3. Annual cargo turnover of road and rail transport in the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2012-2021, million tons

As noted above, most of the piggyback traffic in Uzbekistan is transit traffic. It follows that the amount of cargo turnover should depend on the volume of the foreign trade turnover in the republic. In addition, since the transit cargo flow through the territory of the republic is quite large, it is logical to assume that there is a relationship between the amount of piggyback cargo flow and the amount of foreign trade turnover for transportation services. The dynamics of the mentioned foreign trade turnovers is shown in Figure. 4 [19].

Source: compiled by the author based on data from (State Committee, 2022)

Figure 4. Annual foreign trade turnover and foreign trade turnover for transport services in the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2012-2021, billion USD

Finally, it is obvious that any cargo transportation, including piggyback one, directly depends on the development of the republic's road and rail networks (Figure. 5).

Source: compiled by the author based on data from (State Committee, 2022)

Figure 5. The length of railway tracks (operational length) and paved roads of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2012-2021, thousand km

All the analyzed data for further research using the methods of statistical analysis, are shown in Table 1. **Table 1.** Initial data for analysis

Year	Variables		2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021
Piggyback cargo turnover, million tons	dependent variable	pb	0.30	0.32	0.35	0.34	0.32	0.35	0.36	0.38	0.30	0.35
Cargo turnover of railway transportation, million tons	independent variables (regressors)	rt	61.5	63.7	65.7	67.2	67.6	67.9	68.4	70.1	70.6	72.0
Cargo turnover of road transport, million tons		at	733	801	869	943	1003	1013	1102	1178	1238	1282

GDP transport services, billion USD	vt	16.5	20.6	23.8	26.8	30.6	36.2	44.2	54.5	53.7	67.2
Railway tracks, thousand km	rd	90.6	90.6	89.1	89.1	90.6	95.7	96.9	96.1	97.0	95.5
Paved motor roads, thousand km	ad	59.1	59.0	58.7	58.7	58.7	58.9	58.6	58.6	58.5	58.4
Foreign trade turnover, billion USD	vo	90.6	90.6	89.1	89.1	90.6	95.7	96.9	96.1	97.0	95.5
Foreign trade turnover in transport services, billion USD	vu	59.1	59.0	58.7	58.7	58.7	58.9	58.6	58.6	58.5	58.4

Source: compiled by the author based on data from (Annual reports, 2022; State Committee, 2022)

Pearson correlation coefficient (correlation of moments of productions) is used for variables with interval and with nominal scale. If at least one of the two variables have an ordinal scale or is not normally distributed, Spearman rank correlation is used. Well, Spearman's method is more universal and less rigorous than Pearson's. Pearson's accuracy is slightly higher, but it is not crucial for the tasks. Therefore, it is easier and more correct to use the Spearman coefficients. From the point of view of analysis and interpretation, there is no difference between the Pearson and Spearman coefficients.

In order to obtain adequate results and based on the data in Table 1, the Spearman correlation matrix can be calculated, since the number of observations equal to 10 is not enough to construct a sufficiently adequate Pearson correlation matrix [20].

Table 2. Spearman’s correlation matrix

	pb	vu	vo	ad	rd	vt	at	rt
pb	—							
vu	-0.509	—						
vo	0.295	-0.530	—					

ad	-0.509	1.000	-0.530	—				
rd	0.295	-0.530	1.000	-0.530	—			
vt	0.648	-0.902	0.702	-0.902	0.702	—		
at	0.552	-0.914	0.726	-0.914	0.726	0.988	—	
rt	0.552	-0.914	0.726	-0.914	0.726	0.988	1.000	—

Source: calculated by the author using the jamovi statistical package

It follows from the values of the Spearman correlation coefficients that the most dependent variable pb {cargo turnover of piggyback transportation, million tons} depends on the variable (regressor) vt {GDP transport services, billion USD} and the significance coefficient $p = 0.049 < 0.05$ (at a 95% confidence interval).

Then, according to the degree of dependence, pb depends on the variables at {cargo turnover of road transport, million tons}, rt {cargo turnover of railway transportation, million tons}, at a measure of significance, $p = 0.104 > 0.1$ (at a 90% confidence interval).

Finally, pb correlates rather weakly with ad {paved highways, thousand km} and vu {foreign trade turnover in transport services, billion USD}, at a measure of significance $p = 0.133 > 0.1$.

The remaining variables have correlation coefficients $pb < 0.5$, as they do not correlate with the dependent variable.

3. RESULTS

Considering the correlation coefficients of independent variables, a high degree of correlation and even complete collinearity of some variables (in Table 2 they are marked with color) should be noted. This means that similar variables cannot be simultaneously considered independent regressors.

For a visual picture of the correlation, in particular, the presence of a direct and inverse relationship between variables, one should consider the graph of the density function (distribution density) for the variables (Figure. 6).

Source: calculated by the author using the jamovi statistical package

Figure 6. Graphs of the distribution density of variables

The graph is based on table 2. The size of the light lilac areas on the graph allows to clearly determine the correlation between a pair of variables (high correlation is indicated by thin lines, namely a small area, these lines, as well as in table 2, are marked with light lilac color).

The values of the correlation coefficients with their calculated significances [21], distribution density graphs make it possible to establish a connection between the dependent variable and the factors of impact; however, a more explicit connection of this kind can only be made when building a regression model of the dependent variable as a function of regressors.

Before proceeding with the construction of such a model, one should make sure that the time series for the dependent variable pb is stationary. To solve this problem, it is required to construct the autocorrelation function ACF and the partial

autocorrelation function PACF depending on the lags, and the number of lags should not be less than 5 (half of the number of observations = 10).

Figure 7. Graph of the autocorrelation function (partial autocorrelation function) depending on the lags

The values of ACF and PACF are close to 0 in the interval from 1 to 5 lags with a small spike in the 4th lag, which is explained by a sharp decline and rise in the values of the pb variable in 2020-2021 (Figure 1), corresponding to the crisis caused by the COVID 19 pandemic. However, even this spike does not go beyond the critical values of $\pm 1.96/T^{0.5}$ ($T = 10$ observations), which tells us that the hypothesis of stationarity of the time series for dependent variable pb is true.

We construct a regression model using the least squares method (LSM) for the dependent variable pb.

Table 3. Regression LSM model 1

Model 1: LSM, observations in 2012-2021 (T = 10)

Dependent variable: pb

	coefficient	Statistic error	t-statistics	P-value	
const	4.46419	6.64645	0.6717	0.5386	
at	-0.00106408	0.000421920	-2.522	0.0652	*
vt	0.00303548	0.00195071	1.556	0.1947	
rt	0.0359625	0.0137036	2.624	0.0585	*
ad	-0.108604	0.114260	-0.9505	0.3957	
vo	0.00851596	0.00516440	1.649	0.1745	
Dependent variable mean	0.337601	Stat. deviat. of dependent variable		0.026022	
Sum of sq. residues	0.001605	Stat. error of the model		0.020031	
R-square	0.736648	Corr. R-square		0.407458	
F(5, 4)	2.237760	P-value (F)		0.227614	
Log likelihood	29.49675	Akaike crit.		-46.99351	
Schwartz crit.	-45.17800	Hannan-Quinn crit.		-48.98512	
Parameter rho	-0.130545	Stat. Durbin-Watson		2.215015	

Breusch-Pagan test on heteroscedasticity -

Null hypothesis: no heteroscedasticity

Test statistic: LM = 4.05887

p-value = P(Chi-square(5) > 4.05887) = 0.540972

Breusch-Pagan test on heteroscedasticity (robust option) -

Null hypothesis: no heteroscedasticity

Test statistic: LM = 6.76632

p-value = P(Chi-square(5) > 6.76632) = 0.238607

Source: calculated by the author using the Gretl statistical package

The resulting model does not adequately describe the behavior of the variable pb. This statement is based primarily on the p-value of the Fisher statistic > 0.1 (at a 90% confidence interval). Also unsatisfactory are the p-values of Student's statistic for the regressors, only two of which have this value of less than 0.1. This is most likely due to the presence of heteroscedasticity (heterogeneity of observations, expressed in a non-constant variance of the random error of the

regression model). However, both Breusch-Pagan tests do not indicate the presence of heteroscedasticity. This possible contradiction can be explained by the presence of some heteroscedasticity, revealed by the mechanism of auxiliary regression of higher degrees (greater than 2 degrees) of residuals that the test does not take into account. A more general White's test will fail because the number of variables is very large for such a small number of observations. However, in the Gretl statistical package, there is a mechanism for constructing a least squares model corrected for heteroscedasticity.

Table 4. LSM regression model 2

Model 2: Corrected for heteroscedasticity using observations in 2012-2021 (T = 10)					
Dependent variable: pb					
	Coefficient	Stat. error	t-statistics	P-value	
const	-1.03448	0.235028	-4.402	0.0046	***
at	-0.000831607	0.000185463	-4.484	0.0042	***
vt	0.00456540	0.00124500	3.667	0.0105	**
rt	0.0303216	0.00552823	5.485	0.0015	***
Statistics derived from weighted data:					
Sum of sq. residues	8.415709	Stat. Error of the model	1.184322		
R-square	0.891867	Correc. R-square	0.837801		
F(3. 6)	16.49575	P-value(F)	0.002651		
Log likelihood	-13.32696	Akaike crit.	34.65392		
Schwartz crit.	35.86426	Hannan-Quinn crit.	33.32618		
Parameter rho	0.513849	Stat. Durbin-Watson	0.982780		

Source: calculated by the author using the Gretl statistical package

4. DISCUSSION

This model satisfies the criterion for p-values < 0.05 for all variables, dependent and independent, R-square is close enough to 1, and the log-likelihood criteria, Akaike, Schwartz, and Hannan-Quinn modulo are less than 100, which indirectly confirms the adequacy of the model. However, the Durbin-Watson statistic < 1 indicates the presence of some 1st order autocorrelation, but such a result should not be too disconcerting, since it is characteristic of a series with a small number of observations.

The adequacy of the model is confirmed by the graph of the observed and calculated values of variable pb (Figure 7), and by the residual correlogram (Figure 8).

Source: calculated by the author using the Gretl statistical package

Figure 8. Graph of observed and calculated values of variable pb

Source: calculated by the author using the Gretl statistical package

Figure 9. Correlogram of residuals

The values and criteria calculated in Table 4, the graphs of the calculated and observed values in Fig. 8, and the correlogram of the residuals in Fig. 9 (absence of spikes, ACF and PACF localization near 0) tell us about the sufficient realism of the constructed model, expressed as a regression equation:

$$pb = -1,03 - 0,000832*at + 0,00457*vt + 0,0303*rt \quad (1)$$

The piggyback cargo turnover forecast for the next 3 years calculated using equation (1) has the following form:

Table 5. Forecast of cargo turnover of piggyback transportation in 2022 - 2024, at a 95% confidence intervals, $z(0.025) = 1.96$

Year	Forecast of cargo turnover, million tons	Stat. error	95% confidence interval
2022	0.42	0.0114	(0.394 - 0.438)
2023	0.37	0.0170	(0.339 - 0.406)

2024	0.34	0.0187	(0.300 — 0.373)
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Source: calculated by the author using the Gretl statistical package

The same result is visually presented on the graph (Fig. 10)

Figure 10. Forecast of cargo turnover of piggyback transportation in 2022-2024, million tons'

4. CONCLUSION

To date, the enterprises of Uzbekistan engaged in cargo transportation are increasingly turning their attention to piggyback transportation. Various factors influence the formation of this trend. The correlation analysis of the selected factors affecting the value of cargo turnover of piggyback transportation, as well as the construction of a realistic multiple regression equation shows that the cargo turnover of piggyback transportation directly depends on the value of GDP on

transport services and inversely depends on the cargo turnover of road transportation, which is quite obvious, since road transportation is the strongest alternative to piggyback transportation (it is interesting to note that the correlation analysis shows a direct dependence on the value of GDP on transport services). It can also be noted that there is a direct dependence on the cargo turnover of railway transportation, which also does not contradict logic, since piggyback transportation is a part of railway transportation. But it depends inversely (to a weak extent) on the length of paved roads, which is reasonable, since these roads are used for competing road transportation. In this case, the cases inversely depend (to a weak extent) on the value of foreign trade turnover in transport services, which is an illogical result, probably due to the weak correlation and the small number of observations. Therefore, in order to maintain the given trend and the effective organization of piggyback transportation, it is necessary to form an appropriate infrastructure at the technological, commercial, technical and organizational levels, which will significantly increase the volume of piggyback transportation and give impulse to the development of related areas and directions. At the same time, it is also necessary to take into account the throughput of key railway junctions and automobile junctions. The development of piggyback transportation in the world and in Uzbekistan will give impulse to the development of related areas and directions. Thus, making forecasts for the future development of piggyback transportation in the Republic of Uzbekistan, it is necessary to take into account the degree and direction of the influence of the selected factors. This model is subject to adequate results and its implementation in JSC "Uzbekistan Temir Yullari"

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